

Oxidation of Unsymmetrical Dimethyl Hydrazine by Basic Iodine

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Manuscript received 1 April 1992, accepted 9 July 1992

The reaction of *N,N*-dimethyl hydrazine with I_2 around pH 10.1 has been studied by simple, potentiometric and thermometric titrations. 1.7 mole I_2 are consumed per mole of the base corresponding to two simultaneous reactions, one leading to N_2 and the other to tetramethyltetrazene as products. This conclusion is supported by determination of enthalpy.

The reducing property and endoenergeticity are the main characteristics that make *N,N*-dimethyl (often called unsymmetrical dimethyl) hydrazine (UDMH), $(CH_3)_2NNH_2$, an important propellant component. With concentrated HNO_3 as an oxidiser, a physicochemical analysis of its oxidation products as well as the reaction mechanism were reported earlier¹. Audrieth *et al.*^{2,3} used I_2 for quantitative estimation of hydrazine in acidic media with the following stoichiometric equation,

where $R=H$ or CH_3 .

Cooper and Ramette⁴ demonstrated a slightly different stoichiometry in basic medium with nitrogen as the main product. We were thus led to undertake the determination of stoichiometry of the title reaction with weakly basic I_2 by (i) simple, (ii) potentiometric and (iii) thermometric titrations.

Demonstration of the reaction: No reaction can be observed on mixing the aqueous solution of KI_3 and UDMH. But on the addition of a dilute solution of borax the reaction proceeds rapidly with loss of characteristic iodine colour and some evolution of gas which becomes brisk on stirring. The gas evolved is not brown nor does it turn brown on contact with air. This eliminates NO_2 , NO , NO_3^- and NO_2^- as the sole nitrogen containing product. To confirm that iodine is reduced to iodide only and a quantitative collection and analysis of the gaseous product mixture are too difficult and challenging. Addition of dilute HCl does not regenerate the iodine colour. On the other hand, addition of dilute NaOH to a blank solution of KI_3 resulted in some loss of colouration but this could be recovered by adding excess of dilute HCl. Therefore this reaction cannot be the same as the principal reaction described above and is probably the reversible decolouration due to the reaction⁵,

In weakly acidic solution of iodine, HOI and I^- are present in appreciable concentration, and kinetic studies in weakly acidic solutions⁶ have suggested that HOI is an important intermediate

in the oxidation of hydrazinium ion by I_2 although no information is available on the relative importance of these three species in the oxidation of UDMH.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) are not consistent with reaction (1) and the following two thermodynamically possible reactions may be proposed around pH 10.1,

Which of these is true? This point may appear as dilemma. Both the reactions are consistent with the observed value (4.1) of the ratio of OH^- :UDMH but the choice of pH 5 end-point serves as a quantitative demonstration of the absence of hydroxylamine in the product mixture. At pH 5, the hydroxylamine is supposed to be present as NH_3OH^+ . If stoichiometry (4) were obtained, the protonation of the product hydroxylamine,

would contribute to the apparent mole ratio giving OH^- :UDMH=3.1. Hence one can conclude that actually reaction (3) occurs. Though we have no means to verify tetrazene in dilute aqueous solution, the observed stoichiometry (1:1.7) corresponds to 70% via reaction (3) and 30% via (1).

The last column (Table 1) gives the observed enthalpy of the reaction wherein it has been

TABLE 1—10 ml of 0.005 M UDMH+10 ml of x M BORAX+10 ml OF WATER IN CELL/CALORIMETER VS v ml OF 0.02 M KI_3 CONSUMED AT THE END-POINT

x	pH	End-point (v)		Average I_3^- of the UD- two MH	ΔT	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH mean mol ⁻¹
		Poten- tiomet- ric ml	Ther- mome- tric ml				
0.01	9.5	4.1	4.1	4.1	1.64	0.25	-141.75
0.025	10.1	4.25	4.25	4.25	1.69	0.25	-142.5
0.05	11.0	4.3	4.3	4.3	1.72	0.25	-142.75
0.1	11.7	4.2	4.4	4.3	1.72	0.25	-142.75

assumed that the specific heat of all aqueous solutions used (which are very dilute) are the same as that of water. A comparison of the observed ΔH with the calculated value based on relevant bond energy⁷ and redox potential data⁸ may be instructive. The following energy cycles have been used with the approximation that $\Delta G^\circ \simeq \Delta H^\circ$ for the two half-cell reactions mentioned.

For reaction (3) :

$$2 \times [I_3 + 2e = 3I^-], E^\circ = 0.54 \text{ V}, \Delta G^\circ \simeq \Delta H_1^\circ \simeq -49.628 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2 \times [2OH^- = H_2O + \frac{1}{2}O_2 + 2e], E^\circ = -0.401 \text{ V}, \Delta G^\circ \simeq \Delta H_2^\circ \simeq +36.852 \text{ kcal}$$

$$(CH_3)_2NNH_2 = 2CH_3 + 2N + 2H, \Delta H_3 \simeq 362.619 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2N = N \equiv N, \Delta H_4 \simeq -225.000 \text{ kcal}$$

$$O = O = 2O, \Delta H_5 \simeq 119 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2H + 2O = 2OH, \Delta H_6 \simeq -220.952 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2CH_3 + 2OH = 2CH_3OH, \Delta H_7 \simeq -167.142 \text{ kcal}$$

$$(CH_3)_2NNH_2 + 2I_2^- + 4OH^- = 6I^- + N_2 + CH_3OH + 2H_2O, \Delta H = -144.25 \text{ kcal}$$

For reaction (1) :

$$2[I_2 = I + I], \Delta H_1 = 151 \times 2 = 71.904 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2[(CH_3)_2NNH_2] = (CH_3)_2NN + 2H, \Delta H_2 = 185.238 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2[2H + 2I = 2HI], \Delta H_3 = -282.857 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2(CH_3)_2NN = (CH_3)_2NN = NN(CH_3)_2, \Delta H_4 = 99.523 \text{ kcal}$$

$$2(CH_3)_2NNH_2 + 2I_2 = (CH_3)_2NN = NN(CH_3)_2 + 4HI, \Delta H = -125.238 \text{ kcal}$$

The net calculated of heats of reactions along the two paths (1) and (3) taken together come to $(-144.251 \times 0.7) + (-125.238 \times 0.3) = -138.37 \text{ kcal}$ per mol of UDMH. In spite of the approximations made the agreement between the observed (-142.43 kcal) and calculated ΔH values may be taken to be excellent.

Experimental

UDMH (Fluka), I_2 , KI, $Na_2B_4O_7 \cdot 10H_2O$ and $Na_2S_2O_3$ (all B.D.H.) and HCl (NICE) were used as such. UDMH with due precautions was dissolved in distilled water. I_2 crystals were sublimed before use. The reagent solutions prepared were as follows : UDMH (0.005 M), I_2 in KI (0.02 M), $Na_2B_4O_7 \cdot 10H_2O$ (0.025 M), $Na_2S_2O_3$ (0.1 M), HCl (0.1 M and 0.02 M).

Determination of stoichiometry by titration: UDMH, borax and water (10 ml each) and KI_3 (25 ml) solutions were mixed and its (buffer) pH was found to be 10.1 (solution-A). The reaction mixture was swirled and allowed to stand for 5 min. 0.1 M HCl (10 ml) was then added to quench the reaction and the mixture allowed to stand for ~3 min before back-titrating the excess I_2 with standard $Na_2S_2O_3$ solution. For a blank determination, the mixture was prepared as above but with-

out UDMH solution. An average of three such determinations produced the results, $I_3^- : UDMH = 1.7 \pm 0.01$.

To determine the ratio of $OH^- : UDMH$, it was convenient to initiate the reaction with a measured excess of the standard borax solution and back-titrate the excess with standard HCl solution to a potentiometric end-point. The UDMH, KI_3 and borax buffer solutions (10 ml each) were mixed with water (20 ml) and the mixture was swirled vigorously and allowed to stand for 5 min. The product mixture was transferred quantitatively which formed part of the potentiometric system and titrated with 0.02 M HCl potentiometrically. The end-point, defined in the usual way by the maximum in the slope of the plot of pH vs volume of the titrant occurred at pH 5. At pH 5, not only the excess borax is neutralised but also any hypiodite and iodite formed are reconverted to I_2 . The potentiometric method was chosen both because of the difficulty of detecting a colour indicator in the presence of excess of I_2 and of the relative shallowness of the pH break in borax neutralisation. For a blank determination, borax solution (10 ml) was mixed with water (40 ml) and titrated against 0.1 M HCl using methyl red indicator. An average of three such determinations gave a typical result, $OH^- : UDMH = 4.1 \pm 0.04$.

Potentiometric titration: Potentiometric titrations were performed with the basic solution of UDMH (10 ml UDMH + 10 ml borax solution) in the cell and adding the KI_3 solution gradually from a burette. Redox potentials were measured with a Toshniwal CL 46 Sr 210 pH meter using combined electrode system (Toshniwal CA 11). From the inflections in the titration curves the stage of oxidation was derived. Amount of 0.02 M KI solution vs potential was plotted (figure not shown). The results are summarised in Table 1.

Thermometric titration: Thermometric measurements were made with the UDMH + borax solution in the calorimeter using KI_3 solution in the burette. The calorimeter consisted of a small wide-mouth Dewar-vessel (250 ml) inserted into another Dewar-vessel (1.5 dm³), a thermometer and a glass stirrer. The entire assembly was caged in an wooden box. The space between the two Dewar-vessels and also that between the larger one and the wooden box were filled with cotton wool. The KI_3 solution was kept in jacketed burette through which water at the desired constant temperature (31.1°) was continuously allowed to run. Before reaction the two reactant solutions were thermally equilibrated at the same temperature (31.1°).

The water equivalent of the calorimeter was determined by measuring the heat of neutralisation of 0.25 M NaOH and 0.25 M HCl. Assuming that the specific heat of the solution of HCl, NaOH and

the reaction mixture remains the same as that of pure water, the water equivalent (ω) was calculated,

$$Q_p = 10(t_3 - t_1) + 10(t_3 - t_2) + \omega(t_3 - t_1)$$

where Q_p is heat measured, t_1 the temperature of the alkali (31.1°), t_2 that of the HCl (31.1°) and t_3 that of the mixture (32.1°), and 10 ml each of the acid and alkali were used for the neutralisation. The average of three determinations gave the value of the water equivalent as 14.25 (± 0.1) cal. Volume of 0.02 *M* KI solution vs temperature was plotted (Figure not shown). Table I gives the summary of the results of the thermometric titrations.

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